

Cultures and Leadership for Integration (CLI)

**In Health and Social Care:
Navigating to Successful Change,
CLI Convention Report**

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WEST of SCOTLAND

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Each participant brought a unique combination of professional and personal experience and motivations. Our individual and collective passions often reflect close connections to people who have lived experience of care or caring, at different life stages. We acknowledge all those whose experiences have shaped, and continue to inspire, our passion for care. This report reminds us we must work together across disciplines and across sectors to better align knowledge, lived experience, policy and practice so that the whole of our workforce can thrive, now and in the future, and enable the people they support to live their best lives.

Summary

In uncharted territory it really helps for all to have a good compass. The journey to implementing successful change in a complex health and social care landscape has been, and will continue to be, one that begins in many different places for different people. Having a shared compass with some consistent points of reference can help people navigate to a shared destination, despite their diverse backgrounds and perspectives. Shared reference points or bearings can come from appreciating and using knowledge about cultures and leadership as enablers of successful integration.

This report is a partnership between the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), the Scottish Government and the Scotland hub of the International Foundation for Integrated Care (IFIC Scotland). It builds on a literature review on CLI by an interdisciplinary team of researchers from UWS (Gibb et al., 2024). The knowledge from this literature review was used to inform a one-day CLI Research and Practice convention in November 2024. Evidence and insights from research, policy or practice were sought in advance of the convention to inform discussions throughout the day. A total of 35 cases were submitted and 30 people participated in interactive plenary and small group sessions. A copy of all contributions is published as a separate report (Gibb et al., 2025).

The experience of organising this convention provided a microcosm of the CLI challenges facing health and social care organisations. The number and range of disciplines and partners involved is significant, and one of the underlying challenges of change in this context. The areas of knowledge within scope are multiple and complex. There are historic and current issues with the balance of power, both among statutory agencies and between those in care relationships with the workforce of paid and unpaid carers. These are ongoing concerns, manifest in a particular context in Scotland. Proposals for a National Care Service (NCS), emerging from the IRASC report (Feeley, 2021) have been replaced by plans for a new National Advisory Board¹, reform is still at the centre of very active policy and political debates. Those debates also reflect a changing political landscape in Scotland, and the UK. This report triangulates the key points from the previous literature review, the pre-convention contributions, and analysis of discussions on the day of the convention. The main sections in this report present the following outputs:

- 7 statements about what we know on CLI in the health and social care context
- Analysis of what we need to know about CLI in the health and social care context based on cases provided

¹ While a National Care Service Board as a new public body is not to be established in its place, an Advisory Board will aim to drive improvement and make sure services are consistent, fair and high-quality across Scotland. It will bring system leadership together with people with lived experience to provide advice on leadership, management and whole system improvement in the delivery of social care support, social work and community health services. the Advisory Board's considerations will be informed by diverse lived experience. Their advice will include recommendations on how Ministers might use their existing powers of guidance, direction and funding to secure improvements. There will also be scope for the Advisory Board to advise Ministers on national priorities for integrated health and social care services.

- Priorities for how to discover more together about CLI in the health and social care context, here and now and in the longer-term.
- Some ideas about navigating to change 'here and now' on CLI as a whole.

Together these outputs construct an agenda of change for CLI to impact on outcomes and drive positive change in integrated care. With a new advisory board in place a research agenda further exploring the following questions would be:

1. How can health and social care professionals, teams and organisations implement changes in their cultures and leadership to progress integration?
2. How can successful local, small scale, innovations be better shared and scaled up across a system as a whole?
3. What support and facilitation are needed to enable the above?
4. What are the costs and benefits of providing that support and facilitation of change?

It is intended that this report will prove useful for all partners involved in planning, commissioning and delivering integrated health and social care. Successful CLI will ultimately drive longer-term sustainable changes in funding, organisation of services, workforce and digital solutions. This report is being disseminated to relevant communities of research, policy and practice. It will inform the work of the Scottish Government and national and local health and social care organisations and partners who share a collective vision for integrated care to flourish, however structures and organisations evolve in Scotland.

The recommendations in this report are a call to action, in and across the workforces and system, to invest in CLI knowledge mobilisation, generation of new knowledge and support for knowledge into practice, now and into the future.

The key recommendations are:

- Create and disseminate a 'CLI Compass' guide for individuals, teams and organisations navigating the integrated health and social care system
- Make CLI part of all theories of change for integrated care and a distinctive part of all integration policy and practice, including better appreciation and working with the diverse organisational and professional cultures in health and social care.
- Share case studies on the key elements of CLI and learning from examples of improved policy and practice with all partners for integration to motivate change
- Continue to map 'what we need to know' to focus collaborative research efforts and funding on high impact elements of implementing CLI
- Establish new action research collaborations on the eight Navigators to generate real world knowledge on successful CLI and inform new policy and practice education and training resources
- Increase the range of opportunities for accredited inter-professional and cross-sector education on integrated care at undergraduate, postgraduate and CPD levels for health and social care professionals and partners

A CLI Compass for Navigating Change

Cultures

Navigators

Diverse professional and organisational cultures are acknowledged and valued. People interact through good conversations and build trusting relationships through continuing dialogue within and across these cultures.

Professionals

Do I know what my culture is? Do I understand others cultures? Am I having good conversations about this with others? Am I building trusting relationships through talking about this?

Teams

Do we know what our team culture is? Do we understand others cultures? Are we having good conversations about this with others? Are we building trusting relationships through talking about this?

Organisation and Workforce

Do we know what our organisation culture is? Do we understand others cultures? Are we having good conversations about this with other organisations? Are we building trusting relationships through talking about this?

Belonging

Navigators

People have a sense of 'belonging', psychologically and socially, in places and organisations where they work, and commit to a shared purpose. Information and power are shared equitably across public, independent and third sector partners and with people who access care and support

Professionals

Do I have a strong sense of belonging? Is that about place, organisation or purpose? Am I sharing information and power? Who are my partners?

Teams

Do we have a strong sense of belonging? Is that about place, organisation or purpose? Are we sharing information and power? Who are our partners?

Organisation and Workforce

Does our organisation and workforce have a strong sense of belonging? Is that about place, organisation or purpose? Are we sharing information and power? Who are our partners?

Headspace

Navigators

There is sufficient space and time, in training and in the workplace, to build relationships and trust within and across teams and sectors, and to enable reflection and brave conversations.

Professionals

Do I have the headspace? Am I reflective enough? Do I have brave conversations.

Teams

Do we have the headspace? Are we reflective enough? Do we have brave conversations.

Organisation and Workforce

Do we support enough headspace? Are we enabling the workforce being reflective enough? Do we have brave conversations at the strategic level about the organisation and workforce?

Mindset

Navigators

Professionals and managers blend being both fixers and facilitators and can adapt to deal with uncertainty and change in a complex and dynamic health and care system.

Professionals

Am I both a fixer and facilitator? Do I adapt to uncertainty and change?
Am I thriving in the complex and dynamic?

Teams

Am I both a fixer and facilitator? Do I adapt to uncertainty and change?
Am I thriving in the complex and dynamic?

Organisation and Workforce

Is our organisation and workforce both a fixer and facilitator? Do we adapt to uncertainty and change? Are we thriving in the complex and dynamic?

Outcomes

Navigators

Local, national and organisational outcomes align well and policy, professional and system leaders commit to achieving these outcomes together. Outcome-focused strategies set clear expectations, build long-term trust, and sustain inter-agency collaborations that address prevention, care, wellbeing and population health.

Professionals

Am I aligned to the relevant outcomes? Am I committed to achieving these? Am I outcomes-focused?

Teams

Am I aligned to the relevant outcomes? Am I committed to achieving these? Am I outcomes-focused?

Organisation and Workforce

Is our organisation and workforce aligned to the relevant outcomes? Are we committed to achieving these? Is our organisation and workforce outcomes-focused?

Leadership

Navigators

There is collaborative leadership at all levels and a balance of experienced and emerging leaders in designated leadership roles.

Professionals

Am I as a designated leader engaged in collaboration? Am I an emerging leader in any respects? How well do I support other designated and emergent leaders?

Teams

Are we as designated leaders engaged in collaboration? Are we emerging leaders in any respects? How well do we support other designated and emergent leaders?

Organisation and Workforce

Are we effective working across all designated leaders engaged in collaboration? Are we emerging leaders in any respects? How well do we support other designated and emergent leaders?

Learning & Development

Navigators

Strategic support, collaboration and resourcing of inter-professional learning and development offers a range of undergraduate, postgraduate and workplace based opportunities for inter-professional and cross-sector dialogue.

Professionals

Am I engaged in the right learning and development that includes inter-professional elements?

Teams

Are we engaged in the right learning and development that includes inter-professional elements?

Organisation and Workforce

Are we enabling and engaged in the right learning and development that includes inter-professional elements?

X Factors

Navigators

Other factors which enable success that will emerge as more implementation experience and evaluation of CLI for integration is explored. Appreciating this creates a space for capturing and reflecting about this while using the compass.

Professionals

What am I learning through implementation that is not related to the 7 factors above?

Teams

What are we learning through implementation that is not related to the 7 factors above?

Organisation and Workforce

Are we open to learning more about CLI as we enable success and change?

Introduction

In uncharted territory it really helps to have a good compass. That can enable all kinds of people to plan and make journeys through whatever terrain and whatever environment is encountered on a journey to change. While there will no longer be a journey to change by establishing a National Care Service Board as a new public body, the need to strengthen national support and oversight of the system for integration remains. This means that local innovation and a new Advisory Board will play a critical part in future developments around improvement. Both locally and through an advisory board system leadership will need to journey together in the delivery of social care support, social work and community health services. Locally and nationally all journeys to change will continue to be informed by diverse lived experience and having a common compass in use by all will help to align all around those journeys to change.

Integrated care is a shared vision and aim for many partners in community health care, social care, social work and related sectors such as community planning and housing. It is a vision which engages many organisations, workforces and care system users across the public sector, third sector, social enterprises and independent sector companies. While there are many examples of local successes, a step change in the experience and outcomes of care and support remains elusive. There is urgent need to shift from the prevailing feeling of going round in circles and a crisis driven approach to health and social care that results in fragmented care, rising frustrations and a poor experience for those who either need or provide care and support. The demand for tangible, practical change is strong and persistent but no single and clear theory of change has emerged as a common path to better outcomes.

Currently many may feel somewhat frustrated with the slow progress towards tangible change in integrated health and social care practice. Multiple reviews of policy and practice have highlighted a range of actions that may help drive sustainable change at scale. Integrated funding, governance, organisation of services, workforce planning and digital innovation have all been heralded as routes to better outcomes. Yet none of these levers guarantee success. There will be no sustainable change without acknowledging where people start from, understanding what they uniquely experience along the way, and providing a compass that enables them to navigate towards a shared destination.

One such compass with common bearings to provide direction can be provided for journeys to destinations for Cultures² and Leadership for Integration (CLI). This navigation bearings can offer some consistent reference points for all as they navigate the current and future health and social care landscape. A CLI compass gives a shared direction for all, whether in leadership roles, the workforce or experiencing care and support. This report outlines how a CLI compass has been created and can be used to support professionals, teams and organisations to navigate change.

² We have come to use the term 'cultures' specifically to emphasise that no single and unitary organisational culture for leadership and integration in health and social care; what matters is greater appreciation and respect for the constituent cultures which do, and will continue to, exist.

Multiple reviews on integrated care policy and practice have, or intend to³, highlight a range of actions that enable integrated health and social care to flourish. Changes to funding, governance, organisation of services, attracting the workforce, and digital innovation are all understood to matter, and can become the primary focus. Yet one frequently recurring theme that is not yet well understood is how Cultures and Leadership for Integration (CLI) may enable successful outcomes and can unlock other enablers of long-term sustainable change.

These are not new themes, as concepts like the Quadruple Aim or the WHO European Framework for Action for integrated health services delivery have helped to shift the focus on workforce planning, education and training or role definitions for integrated care (Stein et al., 2023). Who the workforce is, education and training for the future, stronger and better leadership are well established concerns. We need to get beyond collections of stories about this (SSSC, 2018) to a more active enabling of success.

A literature review on CLI (Gibb et al., 2024) suggested that knowledge about CLI in integrated care was limited and fragmented, CLI is not yet well charted. We still have much to do to learn from what has worked – and has not worked – in enabling integration to date. There are many voices and perspectives from different disciplines and from all sectors who can bring valuable research, practice and implementation experience on CLI in Scotland. To hear those we organised a research and practice convention on CLI for invitees from local and national organisations across government, academia, public, third and independent sectors. Appendix 2 contains the list of 30 participants and 5 additional contributors. Those who attended were deeply involved in multiple integrated care projects and programmes, and some people brought perspectives from several roles in different organisations and sectors. Anticipated outcomes were:

- Improved understanding of culture, leadership and integration in health and social care informed by views and experience of people with different experiences of leading, designing and delivering integrated health and social care support and services
- A sense of what we know now about CLI, and what we need to know and do to accelerate the pace of progress of integrating health and social care
- Opportunity for knowledge exchange and partnership building for people who bring different perspectives on CLI – policy makers, academia, integrated care partners and stakeholders
- Strengthening links between health and social care practice and research.

3. Inquiry considering social care for older adults and working age adults. This focus includes personal financial costs, financial costs to the NHS and local authorities, and the cost to the wider economy (including levels of economic activity) we know already that the underlying enabler of change to address cost-framed agendas will be CLI. The economic value of adult social care and how that could be grown, the impact of caring responsibilities on employment levels and hours spent in work, how much the impact of inadequate social care provision is costing the NHS. <https://committees.parliament.uk/committee/81/health-and-social-care-committee/news/203557/health-and-social-care-committee-launches-inquiry-into-cost-of-inaction-on-adult-social-care-reform/>

What We Know

Methods

We drafted seven statements, grounded in the current literature, that aimed to describe what is currently known about enabling successful change in cultures and leadership for integrated health and social care.

1. There is a sense of shared belonging to a culture of inclusive engagement around What Matters to You to reach a shared purpose and agreed outcomes.
2. There are regular 'safe space' opportunities to understand our respective professional cultures and sufficient time to build trust and relationships within and across teams and sectors.
3. There is support for distributed leadership at all levels, nurturing our future leaders while building and retaining useful organisational memory.
4. The culture is one where we share power, nurture innovation, are comfortable with complexity, emergence and creativity.
5. Increase opportunities for inter-professional education and cross sector dialogue, including the voices of people who have lived experience of receiving and providing care and support.
6. We shift our professional and management mindsets to be both fixer and facilitator.
7. There is strategic support and resourcing of continuous learning and development of the workforce in a way that respects rights and promotes stewardship of collective resource.

These seven statements were allocated to sub-group participants at five tables at the convention. Each sub-group was asked to focus on a specific draft statement(s) but could also comment on any statement. Note-takers provided a narrative summary of the discussions about the statements by each sub-group. These narratives were coded with respect to each of the seven statements, and an additional category of miscellaneous elements not specific to any statement. There were 120 discrete elements coded.

Two research project team members independently reviewed the narratives and considered the implications of the coded data for the seven draft statements. This process was followed by an inter-rater conversation and reflection on general participant feedback on the convention (Appendix 6). The final step was to revise the seven draft statements on 'What We Know' and to frame these with some introductory text. These outputs are outlined in the next section.

Convention participants highlighted multiple local examples of leadership and innovations in integrated health and social care. A critical question is why these examples of on the ground leadership and innovation have not been adopted more widely.

“We are awash with policies, evidence and best practices across multiple domains. Understanding how we go about implementing positive CLI is not currently a focus – yet it is probably one of the most important questions to reduce the implementation gap that we see between directives and delivery.”

We know that successful cultures and leadership for integrated care are grounded in a shared purpose, trusting relationships and respect for the diverse roles, skills and boundaries among the various health and social care workforce domains. Critical for successful change is inclusive engagement and appreciation of the voices of people who have lived experience of receiving or providing care and support, throughout planning, co-design, delivery, knowledge generation and evaluation of the impact of new ways of working.

Successful leaders create the conditions and cultures that actively realise rights for all individuals and promote system stewardship at all levels, from reliably managing simple care and support to effective and people-centred care for people with complex and changing needs or circumstances. We also know it is helpful to have common health, care and wellbeing outcomes, as part of a wider set of local and national outcomes and governance.

A CLI reality is that the trust and relationships required to adopt new ways are not generalisable without collaborative leadership that creates the right conditions and cultures. Moreover, the current authorising environment is dynamic and complex with multiple priorities and programmes vying for prominence. This results in a cluttered policy landscape with competing priorities for workforce learning and improvement and a loss of focus on the critical enablers of people-centred, integrated care and support.

Our seven revised statements capture the insights of convention participants on the conditions required to navigate successful change through CLI. The 7 CLI Navigators form our CLI compass along with an 8th Navigator that we have labelled as ‘X Factors’ which may emerge through further research on the implementation of change.

Navigator 1: Cultures

Diverse professional and organisational cultures are acknowledged and valued. People interact through good conversations and build trusting relationships through continuing dialogue within and across these cultures.

People have different ways of working. Cultural differences need to be acknowledged but cultural competency is often lacking, impacting on the practices and behaviours of staff and users alike. Cross-sector mentoring and pathways that recognize individual career choices can foster sustainable culture shifts. Risk averse regulatory frameworks can prevent staff doing the right thing at the right time and can disempower people. There needs to be a clear commitment to balancing autonomy with accountability supported by tools for balanced accountability and frameworks that enable rather than constrain innovation.

We are all the system.

We need to get away from a 'leaders make culture' narrative to seeing culture as a network of behaviours and norms over which leaders have influence but not control.

The current culture is often pivoting around behaviours of 'watching one's back.' An ideal environment would be where managers and practitioners create a collective culture that 'supports one's back'.

Navigator 2: Belonging

People have a sense of 'belonging', psychologically and socially, in places and organisations where they work, and commit to a shared purpose. Information and power are consistently shared equitably and ethically across public, independent and third sector partners and with people who access care and support.

Integrated care should work for everyone regardless of geography, age, gender, ethnicity, or socio-economic circumstances and must move beyond tokenistic engagement to an authentic focus on the community voice. Empowering people and communities to actively shape services ensures lived experiences are equitably integrated into decision-making and commissioning processes. Involving diverse groups ensures fairness and inclusivity to reflect the full range of needs in the community.

Information sharing between services can be difficult. A framework for household-level coordination and methods for integrating different sources of knowledge about individuals and their circumstances, without gaps or duplications, would help all practitioners across the integrated system to deliver high-quality care. There is a need for practical frameworks for data sharing that comply with information governance requirements and respect privacy. Tools that bridge organizational systems and enable informational continuity are essential for dual-system operations. The generational aspect is significant - the younger generation will expect their data to be shared with safeguards in place.

Expectations about sharing information evolve over time – some of this will be generational change.

Data on telecare activations, falls and hospital admissions exists but cannot be shared right now. This is a critical gap in our ability to harness valuable insights from different providers for integrated service improvement.

Navigator 3: Headspace

There is sufficient space and time, in training and in the workplace, to build relationships and trust within and across teams and sectors, and to enable reflection and brave conversations.

Working well together requires trust. Organisations need to value the importance of relationships, recognising that integration is always affected by people working together, systems and structures alone are insufficient. Effective collaboration also requires understanding of how to navigate external relationships with agencies working at different paces or with conflicting priorities. Knowing how to build trust, manage expectations, break down professional and interagency barriers and connect and collaborate across different policy areas supports progress towards shared outcomes.

Leaders and managers need to encourage, enable and support bravery and give permission to staff, at all levels and in all roles, to be involved in creating good solutions and a positive work environment.

Navigator 4: Mindsets

Professionals and managers blend being both fixers and facilitators and can adapt to deal with uncertainty and change in a complex and dynamic health and care system.

Having time to fully listen, observe and respond to what people are asking for is important. This can be enhanced by curiosity to understand different views and perspectives and by willingness to engage and empower professionals and people from diverse communities to be involved in planning and design of services.

The current approach to commissioning creates uncertainty and risk for third sector organisations and social care providers. This has a significant influence on staff recruitment and management capacity. The current pressures require agility, resilience and an ability to adapt to the rapidly changing complex environment through integrated workforce planning, ethical commissioning for fair and realistic resource allocation, and use of evaluation frameworks to demonstrate long-term value from investment.

We need to be brave and have different conversations to influence beyond our core partners in the Integrated Join Board'.

Navigator 5: Outcomes

Local, national and organisational outcomes align well and policy, professional and system leaders commit to achieving these outcomes together. Outcome-focused strategies set clear expectations, build long-term trust, and sustain interagency collaborations that address prevention, care, wellbeing and population health.

Trust is about having confidence in others to deliver shared goals. Currently services are driven by short term targets with gaps in evidencing long term impact for people, communities and systems. Impact data that combines qualitative and quantitative insights provides a more comprehensive understanding of the complex environment of integration, illuminating cultural and systemic changes to guide improvements and ensure sustainability of interventions. Methodologies for integrating multiple data sources including use of lived experience to inform decisions and make real-time service adjustments is paramount. Attention to different needs and being sensitive to cultural differences and inequalities in access and use of services is essential. A review is also needed of staff appraisal and performance criteria with a shift from task and time to user experience and outcomes in the context of consistent reporting of quality.

If it is measured it matters!

What should we stop measuring?

There are significant limitations in effective influencing of behaviours if prevention, experience and wellbeing outcomes are not monitored and reported.

Navigator 6: Leadership

There is collaborative leadership at all levels and a balance of experienced and emerging leaders in designated leadership roles.

In the complex integration environment, leadership must balance organisational stability with openness to innovative solutions. Creative leadership styles and advanced facilitation skills are essential for inspiring people-centered approaches and achieving impactful outcomes. Leadership development must equip current and future leaders with the skills to influence the integration process effectively. This includes embedding creative approaches that prioritise innovation and collaboration.

All front line and managing staff must understand their role and contribution to system integration and quality service delivery. Senior leaders need to have a clear understanding of how different parts of the system work, and what practitioners do on a daily basis. Working towards achieving a commonly shared goal is a key priority. This can be an innovative and transformational process, with cross sector shadowing and mentoring (e.g. 'a day in my shoes') as powerful tools.

We require leadership competencies in integrated health & social care systems and multi-level leadership frameworks that address gaps in middle management and equip leaders with tools for balancing operational and strategic responsibilities.

We do not give enough attention to middle management, where the overwhelming majority of the work (of integration) takes place.

I think we need to get leaders working across integrated services so that redesign and investment fills the knowledge gap relatively quickly.

Navigator 7: Learning and Development

Strategic support, collaboration and resourcing of inter-professional learning and development offers a range of undergraduate, postgraduate and workplace-based opportunities for inter-professional and cross sector dialogue.

Managers need to allocate the time and resources required to develop the workforce to enable integration in practice. Joint training with other organisations adds value to in-house training. To address inefficiencies, we need to eliminate duplication of training and recognise qualifications across sectors and create integrated professional development pathways.

Inter-professional learning is required to prepare the future workforce for integrated care through placements and other learning initiatives in undergraduate/ postgraduate education and continuing professional development. Moving away from selective pilot studies to comprehensive, scalable solutions is vital for long-term success.

We need cross pollination of innovation.

We need to make integrated care the irresistible option.

Navigator 8: X Factors

We acknowledge that there may be other factors which enable success that will emerge as more implementation experience and evaluation of CLI for integration is explored. Appreciating this creates a space for capturing and reflecting about this while using the compass.

What We Need to Know

Both the pre-convention contributions and the dialogue during the convention also explored the gaps in knowledge on CLI needed to create the conditions for successfully navigating change and the actions that can bridge current gaps in CLI knowledge and practice. The following sections of the report provide our analysis of these insights, themed and clustered around the 7 CLI Navigators.

Introduction

Whole system change is difficult and requires novel approaches and solutions, recognising different and changing organisational priorities in a complex system. It is essential to know what works in achieving desired outcomes, and how different elements and innovative ideas can add value in addressing integration complexity challenge. Learning from past activities and projects is essential and requires competence in understanding limitations and gaps in current knowledge. For example, the COVID-19 pandemic showed the importance of relationships between key leaders in the NHS and local authorities at the cusp of aligning systems. These relationships are pivotal for learning how to make changes and make these stick. We need methods for capturing successful crisis-driven innovations, and frameworks for implementing and sustaining positive changes post-crisis to drive integration forward. Additionally, understanding how to scale successful pilot initiatives system-wide is essential and requires practical tools for translating success into system-wide change and establishing mechanisms for measuring long-term impact.

Cultures

What we know about cultures in this context varies. Organisational and workforce themes in NHS healthcare contexts are well studied. Organisational and workforce themes in Social Care contexts, including Local Authorities and multiple private and social enterprise organisations, is less well studied. The interfaces and enablers of success can be mapped in many local cases, though a systemic and generalised account is lacking. These include the appreciation of boundaries between cultures in local places and organisations, and how they are successfully navigated at all levels. The barriers to CLI in practice may include 'sector superiority' dynamics. Tools for measuring cultural change in this context are lacking.

One specific example can illustrate the challenges of re-allocating resources to social care. Cultural barriers and accompanying power relations trump financial reforms (Donaldson et al., 2024), as illustrated by the experience of an intention that all unplanned bed days, including delayed discharges, were to be funded from IJB budgets by transfers to Health Boards, such that an increase in bed days would require more funding from IJBs and reductions would require less; the latter allowing any savings to be re-allocated by the IJB to other services.

Without some Health Board participation in these arrangements, IJBs had no mechanism

for shifting resources if they reduced bed days. This is not confined to Scotland, as one cross country study (Exley et al., 2024) found that in Italy, the Netherlands and Scotland. Health care, and in particular acute hospital care, was reported to dominate social care in terms of policies, resource allocation and national monitoring systems, thereby undermining better collaboration locally.

Belonging

It was acknowledged that current and contemporary policy often refers to (and celebrates the merits of) 'user experience' and 'user voice', but there is very little evidence of service user involvement in the design, management and evaluation of services. There is a perceived disconnect between services and the public who use them. Some participants felt that the distance (practical as well as conceptual) extended significantly after the COVID-19 pandemic following the implementation of several means and methods designed for this very purpose. The legacy effects include reports of reduced human contact and interaction between agency and user. It was suggested that an over reliance on communication using technology has generated a new type of distance whereby agency and user now engage in a staccato relationship which strips interactions of their nuance and humanity. The irony is not lost on participants who made it clear that the service user 'voice' has never been as prominent in the design of policy as it is today, yet the practical distance between users and their services has never been as vast.

Belonging as a theme is also well aligned with the broader set of Community Led Support (CLS) that many will be familiar with, in integrated care and other contexts (Richardson & Pitts, 2023). CLS seeks to change culture and practice so that community health and social care delivery is more clearly values-driven, community focused in achieving outcomes, empowering staff and a true partnership with local people. Implementing CLS taps into the motivation and enthusiasm that still exists across the workforce, and tools like the CLI compass model can contribute to that as part of wider change to move beyond the top-down, 'control and command', cultures. 7 principles of CLS are:

- Co-production at the heart.
- Focus on place and good community and the whole person.
- People getting support and advice when they need it as a preventative support rather than at crisis point.
- Trust and value staff and communities.
- Strength-based support through a strength-based conversation.
- Challenging bureaucracy around what's important.
- System being responsive and supportive.

Headspace

Participants often referred to needing 'more' space and time to do research, to build effective relationships, to engage in capacity building, to network and develop professional connections. This perennial issue features consistently across reports and audits, with many feeling that it is never adequately addressed by organisations (largely due to lack of resources more generally). Some participants acknowledged that progress is often hamstrung by the volume of administrative and bureaucratic tasks expected of them in their agencies. This leaves limited space and time for doing any creative and purposeful work around building professional relationships and making progress around dimensions of information sharing, joint

enterprise and shared responsibility for the delivery of services. Participants felt that we need to develop our knowledge and understanding around why dimensions of space and time keep emerging as recurring barriers to progress.

Mindsets

A clear direction with leadership mindsets and behaviours that promote a culture of hope and inclusive engagement without fear is needed to further motivate and empower people to adopt new ways of working together that are sensitive to differences in cultures, resources, needs and circumstances. Different tools are needed to achieve this. The ideal approach would prioritise investment in developing capability on the ground and allow time and opportunity to make effective integration possible.

We heard multiple observations that different policy teams in the Scottish Government are not well aligned, leading to siloed working. Frameworks like the National Performance Framework (NPF) seek to enable this across government, including health and social care partners. Connecting across policy areas is crucial to effect change, particularly in developing protocols for managing multiple partnerships where different agencies operate at varying paces of change. Strategic policy drivers need a long-term commitment with all political parties coming together around a shared vision for an effective integrated system. This requires practical frameworks for managing political-professional relationships, methods for building sustainable cross-party support and tools for navigating external partnerships operating at different speeds.

The practice-policy gap was highlighted. How implementation of policy unfolds in practice (e.g. the front-line work of delivering services) needs careful attention. It seems that policies are in place to work in an integrated way, as well as willingness from people in the system, however, the current structures are not well enough aligned to support human effort. There are many barriers to working in an integrated way, and these slow progress in moving the integration agenda forward. Not all parts of the system are on board, some partners reject integration, citing structures, systems or processes that are difficult or cannot be changed. For this reason, the focus should be placed on using CLI to drive alignment of a shared aim and adoption of good practice within current structural and financial constraints.

Outcomes

Participants expressed concerns about the complexity and volume of accountability mechanisms and how these impact on growth and progress when each 'type' of agency is subject to different forms and methods of inspection and evaluation. Several participants referred to agencies working to different local and national objectives – leading to different levels of focus on areas of service delivery for each specific agency (or group of similar agencies). This results in high levels of silo working, as each agency stays within its area of practice to ensure that requisite requirements and duties are met. Some felt that a universal approach to accountability would only be achievable by streamlining existing arrangements and implementing a national model anchored by legislation and policy. But it was also suggested that a move towards a universal model would result in losing locally framed approaches to service delivery.

Linked to accountability, a significant number of participants expressed concerns with the consistent process of privileging the nature and value of 'outputs' over 'outcomes' across organisations. Many gave examples where reporting mechanisms often require quantitative

data on people accessing services rather than qualitative data on the reach and positive impact of services on the public. This emerged as a frequent theme across discussions. Participants expressed a need to understand and work towards designing replicable and universal methods of capturing, analysing, measuring and evaluating outcomes – shifting the emphasis away from outputs (consensus that ‘outputs’ tell us little about the broad impact different services can make in the lives of people who use services). Many participants felt that we need further research, development and understanding around our conception of ‘outcomes and how different agencies approach meeting more qualitative dimensions of their own – as well as national – aims and objectives.

There needs to be a heightened focus on integration in Scotland, viewed as an investment in population health and economic growth. Rather than a reactive response to crisis, a shift is required towards preventative care and place-based approaches to population health. That requires addressing underexplored partnerships such as community planning and housing to make meaningful changes such as household level integration with one point of contact for individuals and their families to be rolled out and championed. To achieve this, we need methods for engaging non-traditional partners and communities, as well as frameworks for managing different organizational priorities.

Leadership

As with cultures what we know about leadership, including both designated leaders in formal positions at the top and in the middle of the system along with and emergent leaders locally in teams delivering innovation, in this context varies. Multi-level leadership and workforce themes in NHS healthcare contexts are well studied and provided for with programmes and support. Leadership and workforce themes in social care contexts, including local authorities and multiple private and social enterprise organisations, is less well studied and seems to have fewer programmes associated with this. One concern is which programmes and methods for designated leaders and embedding distributed leadership in organisations for collaborative and compassionate leadership are most effective. Another is how emergent leaders can be developed and supported so that they can flourish in their workplace and lead successful innovations to scale. Specifically, there is a need for multi-level leadership frameworks that address gaps in middle management and equip leaders with tools for balancing professional, operational and strategic issues. Finally, a concern is how better to manage political-professional relationships and build sustainable cross-party support and tools for navigating change in dynamic systems.

Learning and Development

It was recognised that some educational institutions are preparing people to work within integrated environments by embedding principles and opportunities for inter-professional education in programmes across different professional areas. It was felt that this helped to develop occupational cultures that could lead to more ‘connected’ communities of practice once individuals entered their chosen field. We need further knowledge and understanding around the benefits of integrating dimensions of inter-professional education into curricula across professional and allied programmes. We need to understand how best to harness and support inter-professional networks and ‘communities’ in practice too.

For example, to prepare future health care providers (HCPs) to work in integrated care, it is important to include Inter Professional Education (IPE) and integrated care concepts/principles in formal academic training and offer student placements within established integrated care

programs to facilitate learning and competencies early in their career (Bookey-Bassett et al., 2023). Siloed approaches in IPE within and across health sectors can help health care providers understand the focus of the integrated care program (e.g., patient pathways, referrals) and the roles and responsibilities of various team members. IPE in academic and practice settings should include content related to teamwork competencies, principles for collaborative practice, and foundations of integrated care. IPE plays a unique and important role in training health and social care providers to work in integrated care and can be described metaphorically as “a bridge to integrated care (Bookey-Bassett et al., 2022)”.

Gaps in Knowledge

In the next section we highlight specific gaps in the knowledge needed to successfully accelerate progress on CLI in this context.

For each Navigator, we pose a series of research and inquiry questions informed by the lived experience of people with a policy, practice or advocacy role for people who use health or social care support or services.

Navigator 1: Cultures

- Where do boundaries exist between cultures in local places and organisations?
- How can these boundaries be respected and successfully navigated at all levels?
- How can we respect diverse cultural practices and needs.
- What are the barriers in practice including ‘sector superiority’ dynamics, and how can these be overcome?
- What are the most useful tools for measuring cultural change in this context?

Navigator 2: Belonging

- What enables a strong sense of belonging in the health and care workforce?
- What enables and sustains commitment by a diverse workforce to a shared purpose?
- Where are information and power shared equitably across all partners and with those accessing care and support? What stops this from happening?
- How might a ‘family advocate’ role and digital solutions enable information sharing?
- How can we optimise digital inclusion of the workforce and for those who access care and support?

Navigator 3: Headspace

- Why do space and time keep emerging as recurring barriers to progress?
- How do some teams and organisations manage to prioritise and protect time to reflect, learn and improve together?
- How to overcome barriers from professionals or organisations that don't collaborate as they are working at different paces and/or with conflicting priorities?
- What is the art of having 'brave' conversations and how can we embed these in workforce development for all health and care professionals and at all levels?

Navigator 4: Mindsets

- Who and what influences current mindsets in different professional disciplines and organisations?
- How do local and national governance and performance arrangements impact on mindsets and behaviours?
- What can we learn from the COVID-19 experience where there was permission to act professionally and with confidence for making the right decision in the moment.
- How can we support the workforce to 'do with, not to' and become confident facilitators who work alongside people, supporting them to be more resilient?
- What frameworks demonstrate long-term public value including social return on investment?

Navigator 5: Outcomes

- What drives a preference for a focus on Outcomes (Vs) Outputs in different context and for different professional disciplines?
- How do different organisations use and value quantitative v qualitative data?
- How do local and national organisations balance pursuit of short term and longer-term outcomes?
- How can local systems realise rights for all to reduce inequity of access, experience and outcomes?
- What staff appraisal and performance criteria can help lever a shift from task and time to user experience and outcomes?
- What health and wellbeing outcomes for integrated care are meaningful and measurable?

Navigator 6: Leadership

- Which programmes and methods for embedding distributed leadership in organisations are effective for collaborative and compassionate leadership in current designated leaders and should be supported?
- How are emergent leaders best developed and supported so that they can flourish in their workplace and lead successful innovations to scale?
- What multi-level leadership frameworks address gaps in middle management and equip leaders with tools for balancing professional, operational and strategic issues?
- How can we manage political-professional relationships and build sustainable cross-party support and tools for navigating change in dynamic systems?

Navigator 7: Learning and Development

- Which elements of workforce learning and development work best for different professional groups and different context?
- How best to mobilise and support inter-professional networks and 'communities' in practice?
- What methods and tools can enhance Inter-professional and cross-sector learning to shape the present and future health and social care workforce, so it values and embraces integrated care?
- What practical actions strengthen interpersonal connections and foster supportive relationships across professional disciplines and sectors?

Navigator 8: X Factors

- As we experience greater implementation of CLI what new factors are being found that enable success?
- As we evaluate individual projects, responses to change, and system impacts what other CLI factors may be emerging?

This list of questions is not exhaustive, it gives a steer to focus the actions that we can take together to where on journeys to change there may be a need to build bridges across the knowledge gaps. These are set out in the next section.

How to discover more together

Introduction

In this section we highlight general approaches and some specific actions that will help to address the identified knowledge gaps to accelerate progress on CLI.

General Approaches

Incorporating lived experience in research is key to fostering cultures and leadership styles truly responsive to the needs and preferences of people with lived experience. If we are interested in integration from the perspective of the service user, then qualitative study must predominate, drawing on narrative experiences and researchers' observations. We need a blend of quantitative, mixed methods and qualitative studies for a more holistic understanding of impact and to refine our CLI approach.

These methods include:

- Collaborative research projects with external partners, particularly around managing relationships and expectations.
- Sharing best practices, challenges, and successes on how to work with external agencies and partners, especially when their pace or priorities don't align.
- Focus groups and in-depth interviews with members of diverse communities and engagement with third sector/voluntary organisations.
- Implementation science and action research to change things in context.
- Appreciative inquiry and collaborative Critical Creative Inquiry.
- Monitoring impact using quantitative, mixed methods and qualitative data, including impact on population health and wellbeing and inequalities.
- Co-design, collaborative sense-making.

For each Navigator we propose specific practical actions that will

- Mobilise existing knowledge on CLI,
- Generate new knowledge on CLI, or
- Support knowledge into practice to build the confidence and capability of the whole workforce.

Navigator 1: Cultures

- Collate and share case studies of creating the conditions for successful interactions between diverse professional and organisational cultures.
- Conduct research at local and national levels to understand the changes in organisational culture over time.
- Develop cross-cultural frameworks, tools that celebrate distinct professional identities while fostering collaboration and appropriate risk-taking, and provide opportunities for the diverse workforce to understand and respect different roles and cultures.

Navigator 2: Belonging

- Collate and share case studies of inclusive engagement and of the benefits of sharing information and power equitably across all partners.
- Conduct research in local integrated systems to understand perceptions of belonging in different professions and partners and how these change over time.
- Develop learning materials on collaborative decision-making and opportunities for the diverse workforce to become confident in sharing information and power effectively with others.

Navigator 3: Headspace

- Collate and share case studies that illustrate the benefits of space and time to build trusting relationships between different professionals and partners.
- Conduct research at local and national levels to understand how to prioritise and protect time for collaborative reflective practice and how to overcome barriers to progress, including the impact of reduced human contact between agencies and users, exploring the extent to which proximity matters and what could be done to improve this across organisations.
- Develop collaborative learning materials and create opportunities to prepare the diverse workforce to have good, brave conversations together.

Navigator 4: Mindsets

- Collate and share case studies that illustrate the desired mindsets, and ways to move towards these individually and collectively.
- Conduct research to understand how to create the conditions for streamlined local and national accountability in a complex and dynamic health and care system.
- Develop collaborative learning materials and create opportunities to prepare the workforce to shift to being facilitators who adopt strength-based approaches.

Navigator 5: Outcomes

- Collate and share case studies that illustrate a strong outcomes focused approach across partners and steps required to adopt this approach.
- Conduct research at local and national levels to understand how to create cross-party long-term commitment to creating an integrated health and care system that includes underexplored partnerships, such as housing and education.
- Develop collaborative learning materials and create opportunities to inspire policy leads, politicians, system leader and professional bodies to view equitable investment in the health and social care workforce as a route to community wealth building and economic growth.

Navigator 6: Leadership

- Collate and share existing studies of the effectiveness of local and national programmes for developing current and future leaders.
- Conduct research and evaluation of the impact of selected leadership development programmes on both individual and system resilience.
- Develop collaborative learning materials that incorporate the eight Navigators and create opportunities for cross sector shadowing, mentoring and leadership.

Navigator 7: Learning and Development

- Collate and share case studies of embedding inter-professional education and reflective practice in curricula across professional and allied programmes and communities of practice.
- Conduct research and evaluation of the impact of selected inter-professional education on the outcomes experienced by individuals, teams and systems.
- Develop collaborative learning materials and create opportunities for accredited inter-professional and cross sector education and reflective practice on integrated care at undergraduate, postgraduate and CPD levels for health and social care professionals and partners.

Navigator 8: X Factors

- Capture from experience of implementation of CLI what new factors are being found that enable success.
- Evaluate individual projects, responses to change, and system impacts for what other CLI factors may be emerging.

The CLI Compass Framework

We established 7 Navigators for CLI in health and social care integration, grounded in operational experience and reflecting the range of contributions to the convention, and added the 8th bearing of 'X Factors'. We used these 8 Navigators to align 'what we need to know' and 'how to learn more together.' Bringing together all our sources, the pre-convention contributions and cases, the convention discussions among all participants, and the reflections of convention participants on CLI, we have produced a synthesis of CLI for successful change in integrated health and social care in Scotland. This provided the foundation for constructing a theory of change for CLI to drive positive change in integrated care with optimal impact on outcomes.

To convert this into a simple and impactful tool we have created the CLI Compass model.

A CLI Compass for Navigating Change

Conclusions

Creating and using a CLI compass can help journeys to successful change, and ultimately support longer-term sustainable changes in funding, organisation of services, workforce and digital solutions. This complements the reality that professionals and organisations may have their own internal 'North Star', that tells them if they are on the right path; their values, their tacit knowledge, their experiences. When we need to go where there is no path nor any roadmap, and make trails, a compass is essential.

This report offers a compass, grounded in knowledge about CLI from our previous literature review, the pre-convention contributions, and analysis of discussions on the day of the convention. The outputs have informed a compass for all engaging with CLI to drive positive change in integrated care and impact on outcomes. It is hoped that the CLI compass will prove a useful model for all partners involved in planning, commissioning and delivering integrated health and social care.

This report is being disseminated to relevant communities of research, policy and practice. It will inform the work of the Scottish Government and national and local health and social care organisations and partners who share a collective vision for integrated care to flourish, however structures and organisations evolve in Scotland.

The recommendations below are a call to action to invest in CLI knowledge mobilisation, generation of new knowledge and support for knowledge into practice, now and into the future. In addition to the seven factors we have identified, aligned with the model of a compass, we include also an 8th factor, 'X Factors'. These areas are those yet unknown which may emerge as further research is done in the implementation of change.

Recommendations and Research Agenda

Our key recommendations are to:

- Create and disseminate a 'CLI Compass' guide for professionals, teams and organisations navigating the integrated health and social care system.
- Make CLI part of all agendas for change for integrated care and a distinctive part of all integration policy and practice, including better appreciation and working with the diverse organisational and professional cultures in health and social care and as a whole.
- Share in training and education case studies on the key elements of CLI and learning from examples of improved policy and practice with all partners for integration to motivate change.
- Continue to map 'what we need to know' to focus collaborative research efforts and funding on high impact elements of implementing CLI, about the research agenda set out below.
- Establish new implementation research collaborations on the eight Navigators to generate real world knowledge on successful CLI and inform new policy and practice education and training resources.
- Increase the range of opportunities for accredited inter-professional and cross sector education on integrated care at undergraduate, postgraduate and CPD levels for health and social care professionals and partners.

Together these outputs construct an agenda of change for CLI to impact on outcomes and drive positive change in integrated care. With a new advisory board in place a research agenda further exploring the following questions would be:

1. How can health and social care professionals, teams and organisations implement changes in their cultures and leadership to progress integration?
2. How can successful local, small scale, innovations be better shared and scaled up across a system as a whole?
3. What support and facilitation are needed to enable the above?
4. What are the costs and benefits of providing that support and facilitation of change?

References

These are a selected set of resources additional to those used in the literature review that preceded the convention

Bookey-Bassett, S., Espin, S. and Lawrence, K., (2022) 'The Role of Interprofessional Education in Training Healthcare Providers for Integrated Healthcare: A Scoping Review', *Health, Interprofessional Practice and Education*, 4(3). eP2191

Bookey-Bassett, S., Espin, S., Northwood, M., Jeffs, L., & Veerasuntharam, A. (2023) 'There's No Room for Silos. Interprofessional Education in Hospital to Home Integrated Care Programs', *Interprofessional Practice and Education*, 5: 5, 1–13.

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Gibb, S., Hendry, A., Rainey, H., Webb, A., Grant, S., Gamble, S., Mashkoor, A., Hendry, C., Craney, A., Carroll, R. (2025) *Cultures and Leadership for Integration (CLI). Convention Report. All Cases with Contributors*. University of West of Scotland. Social Impact Leadership and Management Research Group, Report 2.

SSSC (2018) *Building collaboration and compassion for integrated working A booklet of stories from the social service workforce*, Scottish Social Services Council.

Stein, K.V., Goodwin, N., Aldasoro, E., Miller, R. (2023) 'The Integrated Care Workforce: What does it Need? Who does it Take?', *International Journal of Integrated Care*, 23(3): 1, 1–3.

Richardson, M., Pitts, J. (2023) *Valuing Community Led Support (CLS): The economic case for strengths based, community led support*, National Development Team for Inclusion.

Other Resources

Nine Pillars of Integrated Care - IFIC (integratedcarefoundation.org)

Community Led Support <https://www.ndti.org.uk/projects/cls-in-scotland>

Appendix 1 Convention Participants & Contributors

Name	Organisation
Sara Redmond	Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland
Margaret Moncrief	South Lanarkshire HSCP Forum
Susie Gamble	University of the West of Scotland
Connie Hendry	Scottish Government, NCS Workforce
Michelle Sutherland	North Ayrshire HSCP
Niamh Lennox Chhugani	CEO, International Foundation for Integrated Care
Julie Gracie	Fife HSCP & You and a Collaborative Leader programme
Rachel Cairns	Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland
Anne Hendry	University of the West of Scotland/ Director IFIC Scotland
Kirsty Merriman	Scottish Government Leading 2 Change
Ben Farrugia	Social Work Scotland
Mohammed Ishaq	UWS SILM BME
Angie Wood	Scottish Government Deputy Director, former Chief Officer
Diane Fraser	Social Work Scotland and North Lanarkshire HSCP
Derek Barron	Director of Care, Erskine Veterans Charity
Awais Mashkoor	University of the West of Scotland
Ian Turner	Scottish Government Deputy Director, Adult Social Care and Fair Work
Margaret Reid Arbuckle	Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland
Selina Ross	West Dunbartonshire Third Sector interface
Grant Laidlaw	Scottish Government
Katharine Ross	National Services Scotland
Aleksandra Webb	University of the West of Scotland
Alyson Vale	Social care practitioner and influencer
Clare Thomas	Scottish Government
Iain Ramsay	Scottish Government Professional Social Work Adviser
Stephen Gibb	University of the West of Scotland
Lynn Douglas	Former AHP Director and CEO Bield Housing
Harriet Hunter	Centre for Public Impact
Kerry Musselbrook	Iriss Research
Clare Cable	CEO Burdett – ex QNIS

Appendix 2

Contributors template

Name	
Organisation	
Role	
Proposed Title for contribution	
What we have done which created knowledge about CLI	
Who/ what made this possible	
The challenges we faced and how we overcome them	
What we learned that others may find useful	
The gaps in our knowledge about CLI that are worth exploring further	
The types of study and methods that may help us bridge these knowledge gaps	
Links to reports / publications/ website for further information	

Appendix 3 Participant Templates and Cases

Provided Pre-Convention

1. Facilitating Change: Creative Approaches to Leadership.
2. Building a Culture of Innovation: The Role of Creative Leadership in Quality Improvement.
3. Designing Improvement: The Role of Creative Collaboration in Leadership Transformation.
4. The Power of Story: Using AI and Social Media to Shape Leadership Narratives in Care.
5. Empowering the Future: Dispersed Leadership and the Rise of Next-Gen Leaders”.
6. Interpersonal connections and supportive relationships to support integrated Health & Social Care leadership: the good the bad and the aesthetically challenged!
7. Improving Wellbeing and Working Cultures (IWWC).
8. Ensuring the community has a voice in the planning and consultation of health and social care services.
9. Composed a Mental Health Pathway Booklet.
10. Part of a Community Panel to set up a UK Capital Health Impact Assessment Tool.
11. Current working across Lanarkshire to set up a Home from Hospital Leaflet for patients, carers and staff.
12. Addressing health inequalities by reforming screening engagement and collaboration across health and social care: reflection and progress.
13. Primary care transformation and integration of health and social care.
14. Supporting the role of Lived Experience Representatives on IJBs.
15. Shaping the Future: People-centred Cultures and Courageous Leadership for Integration.
16. How as senior leaders across sectors can we best lever change by creating the conditions that enable change to happen?
17. Leadership & Culture: Supporting the Implementation of GIRFE.
18. “Embedding the principles of Equality, diversity and inclusion into health and social care.
19. Integrated Health & Social Care - An Opportunity or a systematic process doomed to failure?
20. The role of complex adaptive leadership (CAL) in creating the right culture for successful integrated care.
21. Knowing, Being and Becoming a People-centred Leader.
22. Self, group and system - finding shared purpose and working with the complex reality to turn shared purpose into a practical action.

Contributions provide at or after the convention

1. Anti-racism in social work Statement of Intent.
2. Our No 11. Flagship building in Dalkeith housing mental health, substance use, and justice services is a great example (so it can be done!).
3. Leadership development in practice in Scotland.
4. Experience working across NHS, independent and 3rd sectors.
5. Culture of Integration Co-design report (SG internal) - Commissioner of internal report.
6. Ageing Well - enabling partners to work together to create places, spaces and communities for people to thrive as they age.
7. CONNECT - providing simple access to good information about community supports, alternatives to services and services when needed with a focus on prevention and early intervention through coordinated multi-agency support through high-street drop in, website/app and single telephone line.
8. Ahead of the Curve - using the Lifecurve and frailty index to identify people at very early stages of frailty through volunteer footcare services who then signpost people to community activities to improve function and independence in the long term.
9. Team Around the Locality - enabling teams to work together to provide coordinated and people-centred support for those who need some service support.
10. Getting It Right for Ayr North - a targeted multi-agency approach to improve equality of outcomes in South Ayrshire most impacted on by inequality and the socio-economic impacts on health and wellbeing.
11. Organisational Culture Learning Culture Leadership behaviours.
12. Professional culture/socialisation may be a primary determinant of Transformational Leadership behaviours.
13. Adaptive leadership model & methodology is applicable and appropriate for large scale service redesign.

Appendix 4

Participants Post Convention Feedback on Key takeaways from the event

Leadership

- Real integration will need truly brave political leadership.
- Social care as a public health issue.
- Genuine conversation on shifting resources to focus on prevention and early intervention.
- Many layers to integration (strategic planning and leadership, practice through multi-agency working) does this need different approaches?
- Consider and prioritise succession planning and leaders of the future.
- Permission and creating authorising environments-thinking of the poem on this point-create permission for the 7 enabling culture statements.
- Increase the attention on integration in Scotland, as this has diminished recently
- Commitment to improve things is evident.
- Integration may need to be revitalised in general terms to ensure previous momentum disrupted by covid is not lost.

Cultures

- Culture is multi-dimensional, inter-generational and inter-professional (and inter-organisational) we need to understand what we mean when talking about culture to influence and adapt.
- Measuring culture- see McCormack and McCance workplace culture inventory.
- Culture(s) matter as does collective bravery.
- Culture plays a big part; culture change takes a while but is possible.
- Culture change needed.
- Connect in CLI learning to NMT, IWWC, GMC, etc on culture and community XPS of what we are hearing from the wider system.
- Only true culture change is generational.

Measures

- Need for qualitative outcomes, stories and value of 3rd sector provisions.
- Lived experience needs to be valued and listened to.
- What is the story we want to tell- is it that ten years on services are not experienced as integrated by recipients and staff?
- Difficult and no single solution will deliver desired outcomes- not everyone wants the same outcomes (politicians, the media).
- Reablement- better to measure access to this rather than overfocus on delayed discharges, be careful what we measure.

- Broader approach to achieving outcomes, a shift in what is measured.
- In the story to be told which voices are to be prioritised (recipients and staff) to track incremental changes that are having an impact?
- The contribution of everyone, NHS, LAs 3rd sector. Independent sector, service users and carers all have a role to play, and their agency must be promoted and valued.
- Communication and respect needed to strengthen relationships and not only listen but act upon suggestions.

Implement

- Do we already have the knowledge and need to focus more on the how?
- Integration is now in a different place, a movement towards local research and action requires large organisations to change practice, e.g. CI, NHS.
- There are people working in this way already and a lot of progress - but a gap in knowledge exchange and knowledge into practice.
- Importance of the human element in the debate, strengthening the link between service provider and users.

Complexity

- Embrace the complexity but we need to look more critically at the policy/practice architecture that makes things more complicated.
- It is complex but does not need to be complicated- there are partnerships that work, so how do we harness their enablers from a relationship and outcomes perspective.
- Complexities of legislation.
- Working in an extremely complex landscape, despite this and all barriers a strong passion remains to working in an integrated way.

Space and Time for Learning

- Focus on sphere of influence and control - celebrate the success of the work we do.
- Experiential learning matters, over a lifespan.
- Can we use what we have and develop agile/innovative ways of getting knowledge and evidence short and long term to help reform and improve.
- Working and learning together stops being asked the same thing multiple times.
- We need space and time to learn over the longer term, for all players to come together, networks and ecosystem that influence learning.
- Working together, sharing learning and time to do this, knowledge sharing.
- Share knowledge in joint training for all levels of staff and give them space-time-permission to implement.
- Opportunities to learn at all levels.

Place/Locality

- Integration requires a whole systems approach to resolve pressures and workforce challenges, going beyond H&SC for success, broader community planning.
- Thinking about more upstream (NHS, Primary Care & GPs with community link workers) and downstream (housing, employment, transport) integration.
- Focus on local areas rather than whole system change, and it takes brave leadership to see this through.
- Support is required at national level to help people in local systems, for example action learning spaces.

Glossary

Community Led Support (CLS). Seeks to change culture and practice so that community health and social care delivery is more clearly values-driven, community focused in achieving outcomes, empowering staff and a true partnership with local people.

Continuing Professional Development (CPD). CPD is the planned process of learning that helps people improve their professional skills and knowledge. It can include formal courses, work-based learning, and informal learning.

Culture and Leadership for Integration (CLI). A proposed domain of knowledge, research and practice which spans the constituent constructs and can be explored in community health, social work and social care contexts as enabling successful change.

Culture. The shared constituent cognitive, emotional, and relational elements shaping what makes sense, informing what feels right, influencing individual and interpersonal behaviour across all roles and situations. Culture is used as shorthand for a complex of the 'hard' and 'soft' aspects of organisation and often managing a focal and specific theme, such as 'integration'

Organisation culture is considered to inform the typical and acceptable routines of 'how things are done here'. It can be operationalised in various ways, across a general set of values and behaviours or with a specific focus (for example 'improvement', 'rights', and so on). Some highlight top-down leadership and management as shaping culture, some highlight the intrinsic nature of workforce tasks and personnel characteristics, the nature of the 'tribe' as the origin of culture. There are two dual concerns here. First with culture as the general sets of values and behaviours found in workforces including community health, social care and social work: and culture as a focus of enabling and facilitating integration. Second, with the combined influences of leadership/management and the nature of care as a workforce task and the personnel characteristics of the workforce as a 'tribe'.

Cultures. We use the term 'cultures' to emphasise that there is not at present, nor can be, a single and unitary organisational culture for leadership and integration in health and social care; appreciation and respect for the constituent cultures which do, and will continue to, exist.

Differentiated cultures: multiple groups within an organisation possess diverse and often incompatible views and norms.

Fragmented cultures: differentiated cultures may diverge and fragment to such an extent that cross-organisational consensus and norms are absent. A system may be characterised by shifting alliances and allegiances, considerable uncertainty and ambiguity, and unpredictability.

Integrated cultures: occur when there is wide consensus on the basic beliefs and appropriateness of behaviours within the organisation. Even where claimed, integration may exist only in broad aggregate more than practically realised.

HSCP. Partnerships are responsible for adult social care, adult primary health care and unscheduled adult hospital care. Some are also responsible for children's services, homelessness, and criminal justice social work.

Integration. The relationship between elements which are discrete and different parts of a system. Often in HSC the context as one of three constituent parts (community health, social care, social work) and their inter-relationships. Integration needs to be defined in policy, legislation, and system management. The scope and focus of integration can be set out differently by multiple stakeholders. That may reflect a maturity spectrum, from an essentially unintegrated set of organisations acting autonomously, through forms of greater collaboration, to a system with all elements (including workforces) under the control of a single, central agent. Or it may reflect specific domains that can be identified and worked on, such as information and digital systems, inter-professional teams, workforce terms and conditions, and so on.

International Foundation for Integrated Care (IFIC Scotland). IFIC Scotland is the Scottish hub of IFIC. IFIC's Vision is that people, families and communities benefit from person-centred integrated care and support to maximise their health, wellbeing and independence. IFIC supports national hubs, organises national and international conferences, and produces reports and publications on integration.

Inter Professional Education (IPE). Formal academic training to facilitate learning and competencies. IPE in academic and practice settings should include content related to teamwork competencies, principles for collaborative practice, and foundations of integrated care. IPE plays a unique and important role in training health and social care providers to work in integrated care and can be described metaphorically as "a bridge to integrated care".

Leadership. Most commonly leadership is represented as a set of roles which can be enacted in a range of styles, and is a function which exists at various levels, from the highest levels of a hierarchy to operational teams. Leadership can be usefully differentiated with respect to (a) those who have formal leadership roles in hierarchies and organisations (designated leaders) and (b) those who emerge as, and act as, leaders in contexts of change and innovation. In CLI there are concerns with the combined presence, impact and development of both types of leadership.

National Performance Framework (NPF). An overarching set of national outcomes and indicators for their status. Connecting across policy areas is crucial to effect change, particularly in developing protocols for managing multiple partnerships where different agencies operate at varying paces of change. Strategic policy drivers need a long-term commitment with all political parties coming together around a shared vision for an effective integrated system.

University of West of Scotland (UWS). A Scottish Higher Education Institution with teaching and research expertise in health, social care and social work.

World Health Organisation (WHO). Has multiple areas of policy relevance, and a concern especially with 'ageing is living' as a campaigning and policy area.

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